

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' CREATIVE THINKING BASED ON THE PRINCIPLES OF INDIVIDUAL EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8345289>

Abstract. *The educational system organized in a certain way leads to the direct acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities that the student should acquire under the direct influence of the teacher and the student. The article covers the issues of building the educational process using the principle of individual education, developing students' creative thinking.*

Keywords: *information, education, knowledge, skill, competence, control, management, principle, information.*

Creative thinking is the ability to solve a problem, create or otherwise create something new, whether it is a method, device, art object or form. Development of creative thinking of students helps to quickly respond to any problem and find non-standard ways out of difficult situations. Creativity can be successfully used not only by creative professionals, but also in solving various everyday tasks. Every year this skill is more and more in demand.

Everyone has the ability to build their own logic chains. One of the ways to implement these tasks is the principle of individual education, which allows training of highly qualified personnel who are competitive in the labor market.

In the traditional education system, individual, frontal, group education, self-education and their combination are used. A common component of different educational systems is the information that flows between teachers and students. Information organized in a certain way is a characteristic of a certain educational system. In the process of individual education, under the direct influence of the teacher and the student, the information about the knowledge, skills and abilities that the student should acquire is transmitted through a direct channel, and the information learned by the student is transmitted in the opposite direction. According to the results of the control, the teacher corrects the transmitted information and has a management effect on the student.

Building the educational process using the principle of individual education is effective, but it is economically unprofitable in the context of mass (group) education. In the conditions of public education, this contradiction is eliminated by using various technical means of information transmission and control, which allows successful implementation of new information technologies in teaching, educating students and managing the educational process.

The first step in solving the problems of using new information technologies in increasing the level of training of qualified personnel was the goals of the educational process and their connection with production tasks. In the process of forming learning objectives, those related to practical skills are less difficult, since they are typical for most professions related to learning production activities at the workplace:

- monitoring (type and system of operations, time of individual operations, level of automation, workplace provision);
- analysis of actions;

- systematization of operations taking into account the ratio and relationship between operations;

- psychodidactic analysis, identification of the main set of operations.

Development of students' creative thinking based on the principles of individual education requires the analysis of mental operations, that is, unobservable operations.

The principles of individual education are education aimed at identifying the interests, abilities, psychological characteristics and personal characteristics of each student and creating optimal conditions for their use. Each teacher requires creative thinking, which includes a system of rules that allows finding the optimal solution in various or often any limited pedagogical situations that arise when solving specific problems by certain students. The methodological meaning of the development of such a system of rules is that for its implementation, pedagogical activity should be carried out at the highest level - at the level of skill. To the extent that the teacher has the appropriate knowledge and pedagogical talent, he will be able to regulate the natural processes of human development as a person, to build the strategy and tactics of his activity within certain socio-technological systems.

The ways of acquiring educational information or the methods of forming skills do not differ from each other, as a rule, in this case, they have an individual orientation, they remain the same for all students.

Levels of students' preparation and rules for determining them should be formulated by the teacher and included in the program. Academician, psychologist and philosopher D.B. Bogoyavlenskaya in her research introduces the main component of creative "energy" to activate students' creative thinking, which represents positivism with an important accumulation quality. The important properties of energy allow a new perspective on creative thinking. The scientist considers thinking to be one of the leading elements in the formation of readiness for creative self-development and analyzes creative thinking in detail from the point of view of a psychologist.

From this point of view, D.B. Bogoyavlenskaya considers mental activity in three stages:

1. Reproductive - when a person performs actions under the pressure of external stimuli. This stage describes the social level of the person. Some people feel satisfaction from the actions performed, others are only interested, and mental activity decreases with monotony, interest disappears over time.

2. Empirical - a person performs actions in accordance with internal personal motives, without experiencing the pressure of external factors-motivators. An experienced person analyzes his activity, divides it into levels and chooses the best tools for solving existing and emerging problems from the outside world. A person enjoys such activities and can have creative innovation as a result.

3. In connection with the creative-empirical level, a person tries to solve the problems by himself by fully and deeply studying the ways of solving only one specific problem. In this case, creative goals and tasks are manifested in order to achieve a successful result. At the same time, the inner potential of the individual is revealed, personal resources are activated and motivates the individual to continue and implement actions. According to D. B. Bogoyavlenskaya, activity appears and develops due to the activity of the individual himself, and the scientist characterizes this whole process as creativity [1, 2].

Development of students' creative thinking based on the principles of individual education occupies one of the leading places in the process of self-development of a person and serves as an

indicator of personal achievements. It means that students fulfill their needs, implement ideas, strive for the ideal outcome of the situation when certain abilities and tools are available.

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